

Social Media Used By the Academic Libraries during Covid-19 Pandemic Lockdown to Provide Information to the Library Users

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Abstract: *All the Academic libraries were closed due to covid-19 pandemic lockdown as per the WHO guidelines. The Academic institutions were running online using online platform and using social medias. This new opportunities gives the librarians to use the ICT tools to provide the library services to the library users. Hope initially many problems might be faced by the librarians due to lack of infrastructure to provide the online services. But soon many LIS professional may find the way from this situation and started providing library services to the users and faculty members.*

Keywords: *Academic Libraries, Covid-19 pandemic, Library Services,*

Definitions:

1) Lockdown : a temporary condition imposed by governmental authorities (as during the outbreak of an epidemic disease) in which people are required to stay in their homes and refrain from or limit activities outside the home involving public contact (such as dining out or attending large gatherings) By, Merriam Webster Online Dictionary.

2) Pandemic: a dangerous disease that infects many people at one time. By, Cambridge Online Dictionary.

3) Epidemic: (especially of medicine) of disease or anything resembling a disease; attacking or affecting many individuals in a community or a population simultaneously. By, vocabulary.com

4) Social Distance: Social distancing is a set of measures aimed at stopping the spread of an infectious disease, based on staying away from other people as much as possible. It includes things like working from home, only going out to buy food and other essentials, and avoiding contact with other people. By, Collin English Online Dictionary

5) Social Medias: communications on the Internet, such as on websites for social networking and micro blogging, through which users share information, ideas, personal messages, and other content, such as videos. By, online Britannica

Introduction:-

Whole world was stranded and locked due to covid-19 out spread. The effect was gone to the life of every persons/ human being in the whole world. The education institutions were closed due to the covid-19 pandemic. All the educational institutions were closed for many months as a precautionary measures and

guidelines issued by the WHO and by the local Health Departments and Health ministry of every country. This was an unprecedented situations faced by the people from all corners of the world from new born baby to the very old person. The idea of used of ICT tools and platform were come forward and these platforms were used by the peoples of all over the world for work from home, online learning, organising meetings and for be in touch with the family and friends. The problem of covid-19 gives us an opportunity to take a innovative path so that the life of every human become easier. The use of internet, computers, and mobiles were grown up exponentially in pandemic lockdown period. As we say "every problem is mother of invention and new ideas". This proverb come 100% true in the time of pandemic lockdown and post pandemic lockdown. Every one's life is now blended with conventional and ICT, telecommunications technology.

Drastic transformation is seen in educational domain and in library services may be it college library or university library or public library. Huge online contents are now available on internet in the form of eBooks, eMagazine, eJournals and audio books.

Use of Social Media in the Libraries:-

1) Facebook:-

This media can be used by the Library to create a community of users and can share all the information of library in the form of audio-visual and photos. This is a very popular media among the students and common citizens. Due to its versatile usability it is very useful for the library.

2) YouTube:-

YouTube is a free-hosting video streaming websites that allows all members to watch, store and share. The librarian can organised any program of library in real time by sending the link to the users. Live streaming is possible in Youtube. The audience may as many as possible without restriction on viewers. Pre recorded videos can be uploaded on the YouTube and the videos can be saved in the playlist for long time till we delete the video from the playlist.

3) Twitter:-

Twitter is a micro blogging and social networking service on which users post and interact with messages known as 'tweets'. We can tweet text, video, audio or links. This messages or tweets can be share very quickly to the masses and the reactions of the users or the feedback of the users can be seen in the form of retweets. This social media can be used to inform the students about any events or for asking any query to the librarian related to reference service or the book available in the collections.

4) Whatsapp:-

This social media is very popular among the netizens or the common citizens and students for sharing the text messages, videos, audio and photos. It allows users to send text messages and voice messages, make voice and video calls, and share images, documents, user locations, and other content. The librarian can share useful links, pdf files, docx files, ebooks, ejournals need by the users as an when requested by them.

5) Telegram:-

Telegram is a globally free accessible, cross-platform, cloud-based instant messaging service. The service also provides end-to-end encrypted video calling, VoIP, file sharing and several other features. Telegram has its own benefits as there is no limit for the joining of members in the group. The messages can be deleted two sided at any time without any time or period restrictions. In the covid-19 lockdown Telegram get more importance for sharing the information to the students, teachers and faculty members of the colleges and educational institutions. As it is nearly resembles to the Whatsapp but the features wise it is one step ahead of it.

6) Google meet app:-

Google Meet is Google's video conferencing app that is available to everyone who has a Google account. An online meeting is easy to set up whether you are an individual getting together with a couple of friends or a small meeting conducting a workshop online.

Google meet do not restrict regarding the time. It is freely available for all the Google account holders. As many members can join the meeting by opening the shared link of the meeting. The Library can be used this meeting app for short discussion on a topic or a short lecture arranged for the students.

7) Zoom meeting app:-

Zoom is a cloud-based video communications app that allows you to set up virtual video and audio conferencing, webinars, live chats, screen-sharing, and other collaborative capabilities. This app has its benefits and shortcomings also. It has many features provided to the organisers for sharing, recording, chatting, messaging. But the free time given to the organiser is very less. If you want more time for the meeting then you have to pay for that to the zoom. Long meeting, conferences, seminars, workshops can be organised by using zoom meeting app by the Library.

8) Instagram:-

Instagram is a free photo and video sharing app. Library professionals can upload photos or videos of their service and share them with their followers or with a select group of Students and faculty members. They can also view, comment and like posts shared by the students, users and faculty members on Instagram.

Conclusion:-

Covid-19 pandemic was an unprecedented situation come across the whole world. After many years such situation stands in front of every citizen of the whole world. The entire world was stand still cut from each other. Social distancing was another factor which keeps away from each other. This situation also affects the educational institutions and teaching faculties all over the world. The use of social medias and online platform took place to reach out the students and teachers. The library was also not untouched to the use of ICT and online opens access platforms. The librarian provides services to the users by using the social medias and other online platforms for organising the library programs and providing information services to the users.

References:-

1. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/lockdown> (access on 1/08/2022)
2. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/pandemic> (access on 1/08/2022)

3. <https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/epidemic> (access on 1/08/2022)
4. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/social-distancing> (access on 1/08/2022)
5. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/social-media> (access on 1/08/2022)
6. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook> (access on 1/08/2022)
7. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/YouTube> (access on 1/08/2022)
8. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Twitter> (access on 1/08/2022)
9. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/WhatsApp> (access on 1/08/2022)
10. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telegram_\(software\)#:~:text=Telegram](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telegram_(software)#:~:text=Telegram) (access on 1/08/2022)
11. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zoom_Video_Communications (access on 1/08/2022)
12. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Google_Meet (access on 1/08/2022)
13. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Instagram> (access on 1/08/2022)
14. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4262/> (access on 1/08/2022)